

GREEN CONSUMERISM: CONSUMERS' PERCEPTION TOWARDS ORGANIC PRODUCTS IN DOMBIVLI CITY

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Abstract:

There is a great deal of discussion on environmental issues of the business and is expressed by both manufacturers and consumers. One of the popular and professional press in business is "Green Marketing". Green Marketing is the practice of producing, consuming, recycling and disposing products that are less burdensome to the environment. Consumers have also realized the importance of green environment and demands product that undergoes eco-friendly production process which has encouraged "Green Consumerism". Green Consumerism is the consumer who is mindful about the environmental issues and obligations and is supportive to switch from one product to another, which is an organic product even if the cost is higher. The production of organic products has an ecological management production system and are chemical free products. It is a management practice that restore, maintain and enhance "ecological harmony". The production process affects the environment and it is a serious issue, so the researcher thought that the research study should be based on green consumerism and to study about the preferences of the customers to consume organic products. The study is based on primary data. The research will be used by business entrepreneurs and co-jointly by general public.

Key words - *Green Marketing, Green Consumerism, Organic Products, Consumer Perception*

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Introduction:

Green marketing is producing and promoting environmentally friendly products. There is a need to focus on green marketing because of global warming. The companies are trying to differentiate their products from their competitors by creating a niche market for themselves. Green Marketing is also termed as “Environmental Marketing” and was given prominence in 1980s and 1990s after the proceeding of the first workshop on Ecological Marketing held in Austin Texas (US) in 1975. Engaging in these sustainable activities can lead to creating a new product line that caters to a new target market and encourages green consumerism.

Green consumerism refers to a state in which consumers demand the products that have undergone an eco-friendly production process. In this modern era, the social attitude aims people to be aware about the production process which encourage them to buy and sell the products and services which do not harm the nature. The Government of India launched an Eco mark scheme in 1991 to increase consumer awareness in respect of environment friendly product. Green consumerism has created a balance between the buyer’s behaviour and the organization’s profit objectives as it is mainly based on the sustainable and pro-environmental behaviour of consumers.

Organic products / green products are the products which are recyclable, reusable and biodegradable in nature. Products which are produced with natural ingredient, recycled material or non-toxic chemicals. The products which are not harming and polluting the environment.

Green Consumer behaviour and their purchasing preferences are changing. Earlier people were not concerned much about the environment but nowadays customers’ ethical responsibility towards sustainability of environment is increasing. There are few companies and industries in India which are coming up with the techniques of green marketing to inculcate the green consumerism among the consumers. Examples of such companies and industries are - Hotel industry, Wipro’s green, Lead free paints from Kansai Nerolac, organic cosmetics by Sugar company, Lawless, Nykaa companies etc. Such companies are promoting and started selling multiple organic products in India.

Organic India Company Pvt. Ltd., a multi-national company founded in 1997 by spouses Bharat Mitra and Bhavani Lev, in Lucknow, India, that produces organic herbal and Ayurvedic health products sells variety of organic products which supports health and true wellness among the customers. They are committed of being a trustworthy and

innovative global leader by providing genuine True Wellness products. Companies advanced processing methods and dehydration technologies ensure that the herbs retain the maximum level of potential for the highest quality, most effective, pure and natural products available in the market today. The company gives “The Organic Farming Innovation Award” and “The Organic India Dharti Mitr Award” to organic farmers every year to encourage organic farmers all over India.

Review of Literature

1. Bhatia, Mayank and Jain Amit (2013) study about the consumer perception and preferences towards green marketing and focused on the awareness of the consumers towards green products and suggest the marketers to come up with new organic products and communicate the same to the consumers.
2. Cess J. Gelderman, Jos Schijns, Wim Lambrechts, Simon Vijgen (2021) The research highlighted on Green Marketing as an environmental practice and focused on the impact of green satisfaction and green loyalty in a business-to-business.
3. Deepthi Nivasini (2020) The research is based on consumer’s preference towards green products in Thoothukudi. The manufacturers should focus on quality of organic product as the researchers found that the consumers are ready to pay premium price for quality organic product.
4. Shivani Kalra, Dr. Shailja Dixit and Dr. Bobby W. Lyall (2020) The research studies about the impact of consumer preference on demand of organic food products in India. The youth generation are the majority customers for organic product and just the price of the organic product proves to be the only hurdle of less consumption.
5. Dr. N. Savithri and B. Lavanya (2019) The study on perception of Indian Consumers for Organic Food Products. The consumers preference towards organic product change on bases of two factor perception - taste and chemical free product for their good health.

Objectives of the study

1. To study about green marketing and green consumerism.
2. To study the consumer perception towards organic products.
3. To study the factors affecting the consumption of organic products.

Hypothesis

H₀ (Null Hypothesis) - There is no significance difference between gender and frequency of using different types of organic products.

H₁ (Alternate Hypothesis) - There is a significance difference between gender and frequency of using different types of organic products.

Scope of the study

The study is focused on green consumerism and consumer perception towards organic products. It also focuses on the factors affecting consumers behaviour and the reasons of not buying the organic products. In India we all are facing incredible environmental adverse changes hence, this study will try to assist the consumers to demand more goods and services which are based on pro-environment benefits.

Research Methodology

The methodology adapted for this study is based on primary data. The study has tried to assembled the data from consumers of all age groups. The data of 110 respondents is generated via structured questionnaire method from city of Dombivli for analysis.

Tools and Techniques used for analysis

The statistical analysis carried out in the study is being done by using Ms-Excel. The statistical techniques is Chi Square Test is applied.

Limitations of the study

1. The responses for the study is confined to geographical region of Dombivli city only.
2. Time and resource constraint.
3. This research is restricted towards organic products.

Research Analysis

Table 1 Demographic Profile of Respondents

Sr .N o.	Demographic Profile of Respondents	Attributes	Frequency	Percent age %
1	Gender	Male	57	51.8
		Female	53	48.2
2	Age	18 – 40	48	43.6
		41 – 60	41	37.3
		61 – 80	21	19.1
3	Qualification	SSC	13	11.8
		HSC	13	11.8
		Graduation	32	29.1
		Post-Graduation	39	35.5
		Professional	13	11.8
4	Occupation	Service	54	49.1

		Business	14	12.7
		Profession	13	11.8
		Housewife	19	17.3
		Others	10	9.1
5	Income	up to 25,000	40	36.4
		25,000 - 50,000	42	38.2
		50,000 - 75,000	14	12.7
		Above 75,000	14	12.7
6	Awareness about Green Consumerism	Yes	84	76.4
		No	26	23.6
7	Have you ever used organic product	Yes	90	81.8
		No	20	18.2

(Source - Primary data)

Table 1 exhibits that 51.8% are male and remaining 48.2% are female. Table indicates 49.1% respondents are service oriented, 12.7% are businessmen, 11.8% are professionals, 17.3% are housewives, remaining 9.1% belong to other category. It indicates 76.4% are aware about green consumerism and 81.8% respondents have used organic products.

Table 2 Frequency of using different types of organic products

Types of Organic Products	N	AN	O/S	AE	FU
Fruits & Vegetables	(7,8)	(2,3)	(29,33)	(4,8)	(11,5)
Grocery & Staples	(8,14)	(3,5)	(29,27)	(6,7)	(7,4)
Beverages & Juices	(8,14)	(7,7)	(29,26)	(6,6)	(3,4)
Personal Care	(9,9))	(8,6)	(23,32)	(9,5)	(4,5)
Health Care	(9,13)	(7,7)	(26,28)	(6,6)	(5,3)
Snacks	(11,23)	(6,6)	(26,22)	(4,4)	(6,2)

(Source - Primary data)

The table indicates that many consumers have started buying different types of organic products either occasionally/ sometimes.

Table 3 Reasons to purchase organic products

Reasons to purchase Organic Products	SA	A	N	D	SD
Good Health (High Nutritional Value)	43	43	20	3	1
Quality of organic product	42	40	23	5	0
Organic products are fresh and clean	34	43	30	1	2
Hassel-free from GMO (Genetically Modified Organism)	20	51	28	8	3
Social Responsibility in safeguarding environment	33	48	23	6	0

(Source - Primary data)

The above table indicates that the 78% of consumers agreed that the organic products provide good health, organic products are fresh & clean, hassel-free from GMO and they believe that it is a social responsibility of customers to safeguard the environment by using organic products.

Table 4 Reasons for not using organic products

Reasons to not purchase Organic Products	SA	A	N	D	SD
Lack of awareness about organic product	10	59	28	9	4
Price of the organic product	9	46	25	7	3
Easily not available in local market	25	57	20	6	2
Taste of the organic product	10	34	47	15	4
Lack of advertisement on T.V. / Social media	15	54	29	9	3
Lack of awareness about the benefits of organic products	22	47	26	12	3
Not affordable as per expenditure budget	28	33	36	11	2
Varieties are not available (Size, shape, quantity etc.)	20	50	23	15	2
Packaging and display not attractive	12	37	38	17	6

(Source - Primary data)

From the above table it is highlighted that the major factors for not buying organic products are lack of awareness about the organic product due to lack of advertisement on T.V./ social media also the organic products are not easily available in local market as per the customers requirement and in some cases the prices are too high which is not

affordable to middle class customers.

Table 5 Level of awareness of organic products

Reasons to purchase Organic Products	SA	A	N	D	SD
I am aware about organic products	30	61	15	4	0
I feel organic products are safe and hygienic	36	54	20	0	0
I feel food grown organically is environmental friendly	36	56	17	1	0
I feel organic product consumption will reduce pollution and sustain the environment	38	47	24	1	0

(Source - Primary data)

The above table indicates that the maximum realize that the organic products are safe and hygiene and the consumption of organic product will reduce the pollution and sustain the environment.

Table 5 Result of Chi - Square Test

Calculate Value	Table Value	Degree of Freedom	Level of Significance
3.11	11.07	5	5%

Calculated value of Chi-square is 3.11 which is lesser than critical value 11.07 at 5 degree of freedom and 95% level of confidence. The critical value is greater than the calculated value therefore the null hypothesis is accepted. Since, it can be concluded that there is no significant difference among the gender and the frequency of buying different types of organic products.

Findings

1. The research reveals that maximum customers have started buying organic products as they believe that organic products are good for health, fresh and are hassel-free from GMO
2. It was found from the study the major factors affecting the buyers’ perception for organic products are prices unavailability of organic products in local markets and in case of uneducated citizens the lack of awareness for organic products.
3. There is a realization among customers that organic products are safe and hygiene and the consumption of organic products will reduce the pollution and sustain the environment.

4. There is no significance difference among gender and the frequency of buying different types of organic products.

Suggestions

1. To increase the purchasing power of consumers the companies can re-frame their price policy so that the lower-level income group can buy more and more organic products.
2. To create the awareness amongst the customers about the organic products, the companies should focus more on creative/attractive advertisement.
3. To reach the organic products at every corner of the city, companies should develop and focus on a good supply chain management.
4. It is a social responsibility of every citizen to safeguard the environment by switching to organic products.

Conclusion

Nowadays, maximum customers are aware about the environmental challenges which are directly affecting to their health. Due to adverse effect of environment, we should force the customers to buy more and more green products which leads to green consumerism. Government should take a lead to support and promote the companies who have been already adopted green marketing. Government should also organize the campaigns to create green consumerism awareness among the public.

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